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The Evaluation of the Current Production Capacity of Industry in Europe

On average between 2020q3 and 2022q4 it decreased by -60.70%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the current production capacity. It is a value that summarizes the current level of the ability to use production plants.

Ranking of the value of the current production capacity in 2022q4. Belgium is in the first place due to the value of the current production capacity measured in 2022q4 with a value equal to 24.8 units, followed by Ireland with a value of 17.9 units and by Italy with a value of 17.5 unit. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with a value of 6.8 units, followed by Portugal with a value of 5.7 and Austria with a value of 5.4 units. Sweden's ranking close with a value equal to -7.0 units, followed by the Netherlands with a value equal to -7.3 units and the North Macedonia a value equal to -9.7 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage variation of the production capacity between the third quarter of 2020 or 2020q3 and the fourth quarter 2022 or 2022q4. Albania is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the production capacity between the third quarter of 2020 and the fourth quarter 2022 with a value of 263.16% equal to an amount of 10.00 units, followed by Turkey with a amount of 112.82% equal to 4.40 units and from Romania with a value of 105.56% equal to an amount of 1.90 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Czech Republic with an amount equal to -50.00% equal to an amount of -12.90 units, followed by Finland with a value equal to -55.88% equal to an amount of -19, 00 Unit, and Denmark with a value equal to -58.02% equal to an amount of -15.20 units. Sweden's ranking close with an amount equal to -125.00% equal to an amount of -35.00 unit, followed by France with a value equal to -185.71% equal to an amount of -11.70 units, and the Netherlands with a value equal to -661.54% equal to an amount of -6.00 unit.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is proposed below. The analysis shows the presence of two different cluster forms indicated as follows:

- Cluster 1: Greece, Belgium, Slovakia, Italy, Hungary, Czech Republic, Germany, France, Portugal, Spain, Croatia, Malta, Serbia, Albania, Luxembourg.
- Cluster 2: Netherlands, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Cyprus, Sweden, Turkey, Bulgaria, Romania, Slovenia, Poland, Latvia, Lithuania, Denmark, Estonia, Austria, Ireland, Finland.

From a strictly numerical point of view it is possible to calculate the value of the median of the clusters. It is therefore possible to verify that the value of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 12.9 units, while the value of Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 0.6 units. It therefore follows that the following ordering of the clusters is $C1=12.9 > C2=0.6$. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the countries of Central-Southern Europe have a value of the evaluation of the industrial production capacity higher than the corresponding value of the countries of the North-East cluster.

Network Analysis using Manhattan distance. Through the use of the Manhattan distance it is possible to identify complex network structures and simplified network structures. In particular, two complex network structures and three simplified network structures are identified. The following complex network structure is detected, i.e.:

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- Lithuania has a connection with Poland worth 0.9 units;
- Poland has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.9 units, with Latvia for a value equal to 0.55 units, with Romania for a value equal to 0.59 units, with Bulgaria for a value equal to 0.87 units and with Turkey with a value equal to 0.53 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Bulgaria worth 0.62, with Turkey worth 0.7, with Romania worth 0.52, and with Poland for a value equal to 0.55 units;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Latvia for a value equal to 0.62, with Poland for a value equal to 0.87 units, with Romania for a value equal to 0.53 units and with Turkey for a value equal equal to 0.64 units;
- Turkey has a connection with Bulgaria for a value equal to 0.64 units, with Latvia for a value equal to 0.7 units, with Romania equal to an amount of 0.33 units, with Poland equal to an amount of 0.53 units;
- Romania has a connection with Turkey with an amount of 0.33 units, with Bulgaria with a value of 0.53 units, with Latvia with a value of 0.52 units, with Poland with a value by 0.59 units.

There is a complex network structure between the following countries namely:

- Luxembourg and Portugal have a connection worth 0.93 units;
- Portugal has a connection with Luxembourg equal to the amount of 0.93 units, and with Serbia equal to an amount of 0.66 units.
- Serbia has a connection with Portugal worth 0.66 units.

There are three complex network structures made up of the following countries:

- Estonia and Austria have a connection equal to an amount of 0.77 units;
- Denmark and Slovenia have a connection equal to the amount of 0.79 units;
- Belgium and Greece have a connection equal to a value of 0.61 units.

Conclusions. Overall, in the period considered, the value of the valuation of the production capacity decreased by an amount equal to -60.70% equal to an amount of -9.3%. From a metric point of view, the value of the evaluation of the current industrial production capacity decreased continuously between 2020Q3 and 2022Q1, going from an amount of 15.3 to a value of -1.3 units. Subsequently, the average value of the assessment of the current industrial production capacity for the countries considered started to rise again starting from 2022Q2 up to 2022Q4, going from an amount of -0.6 units up to a value equal to 6.0 units. Certainly the valuation value of productive capacity has decreased in Europe in connection with the triple crisis of Covid-19, inflation and war in Ukraine. However, it should be considered that the assessment of industrial production capacity began to show positive trends starting from the third quarter of 2021. This recovery, still weak, could in any case be compromised by further inflationary trends, the incipient economic crisis and further international frictions produced both by the Russian-Ukrainian conflict and by the adverse consequences of the Sino-American tension.

Declarations

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Appendix

Media della Valutazione della Capacità Produttiva Industriale Attuale.

Clusterizzazione C1>C2

